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Study On The Effect Of Chimney Height On The Performance Of A Wood Stove

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of chimney height on the thermal performance of a locally fabricated wood stove. Four stoves of identical geometry but different chimney heights (50 cm, 100 cm, 150 cm, and 200 cm) were tested using the standard Water Boiling Test (WBT). The key performance indicators were thermal efficiency, time to boil three litres of water, and heat storage. The results showed that efficiency increased with chimney height up to 150 cm (31.7%) and then slightly declined at 200 cm (31.0%). The shortest boiling time (21 min) also occurred at 150 cm. Heat storage times remained nearly constant at around 19 minutes for all heights, indicating that chimney height had minimal influence on post-combustion thermal retention. Polynomial regression revealed strong correlations ($R^2 > 0.98$) between chimney height and both efficiency and boiling time, confirming an optimal performance at 150 cm. These findings demonstrate that appropriate chimney design can significantly enhance combustion and thermal transfer efficiency in improved wood stoves fabricated from local materials.

Keywords: Chimney height, wood stove, efficiency, time to boil, heat storage, draft.

INTRODUCTION

Cooking with biomass, especially wood, remains a primary energy source for many households in low- and middle-income regions, particularly in rural settings where alternative fuels are less accessible or affordable. Despite its ubiquity, conventional wood stoves are often characterized by low thermal efficiency, extended cooking times, elevated fuel consumption, and high pollutant emissions, leading to adverse environmental and health impacts (Bailis, *et al.*, 2015; Deng, 2023). The development and optimization of improved cookstove designs are therefore central to efforts aimed at enhancing energy access, reducing deforestation, lowering emissions, and improving indoor air quality (Deng, 2023; Gumino *et al.*, 2020).

A critical design parameter that exerts significant influence on stove performance is chimney height. Chimney height affects the stack (buoyant) draft generated, which in turn drives airflow through the combustion zone, influences gas velocity, residence time of hot gases, heat transfer to the cooking pot, and convective losses up the flue (Agenbroad, 2011; Jetter, *et al.*, 2012). In principle, increasing chimney height enhances buoyant draft by generating a larger pressure differential between the hot exhaust column and ambient air, thereby improving air supply, exhaust removal, and combustion intensity. However, beyond an optimal height, excessive draft or elevated exhaust gas velocities may reduce the effectiveness

of heat transfer to the pot or increase convective heat loss, diminishing returns on performance (Erin, *et al.*, 2021).

Several prior studies have explored the influence of chimney geometry on stove performance, albeit with varying degrees of comprehensiveness. For example, Erin *et al.*, (2021) investigated biomass cookstoves with multiple chimney heights and air intake configurations, finding that both chimney height and air-port opening significantly influence thermal efficiency, emissions, and combustion behaviour. In their experiments, an intermediate chimney height yielded optimal performance before gains diminished at taller chimney configurations. Similarly, Faisal *et al.*, (2018) conducted both experimental and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analyses on double-pot biomass stoves with varied chimney heights. Their study indicated an optimal chimney height of approximately 1.65 meters, at which gas temperatures at both pots were maximized, improving heat transfer and stove efficiency. Also, Dorvlo, *et al.*, (2018) compared two chimney configurations using CFD, showing that distinct chimney designs yield meaningful differences in airflow, internal temperature distribution, and heat transfer.

Beyond chimney height studies, broader reviews of biomass cookstove design emphasize the importance of matching draft, combustion chamber geometry, insulation, and fuel–air mixing to maximize efficiency (Deng, 2023). Agenbrood (2011) proposed a simplified model linking natural convection and stove draft, showing that stove performance is sensitive to chimney height, diameter, and the distance between cook pot and flue. In laboratory stove testing, Jetter *et al.*, (2012) examined a wide variety of cookstove designs and found that chimney-equipped stoves outperformed open-fire stoves, though performance gains depended on a delicate balance of draft, airflow control, and gas–surface heat transfer.

Despite the existing literature, gaps remain: few studies systematically examine three interconnected performance metrics, thermal efficiency, time to boil water, and heat storage (post-combustion cooling), within a single stove design by varying only chimney height. Most prior work isolates efficiency or emissions, seldom connecting those to cooking time or residual heat retention. Time-to-boil is a practical user metric: shorter boiling time translates into lower fuel consumption per cooking session and improves user convenience. Heat storage, that is how long a stove retains useful thermal energy after combustion ceases, is equally important for residual heating, comfort, or secondary uses of stored heat.

From a theoretical standpoint, the relationship between chimney height and these metrics is expected to be nonlinear. Initially, as chimney height increases from a low baseline, performance, efficiency, time to boil, should improve substantially due to enhanced draft and better combustion. However, once the chimney becomes too tall, negative effects such as excessive draft, premature gas exhaust, and increased heat loss may reverse or flatten the trend (Erin *et al.*, 2021; Faisal *et al.*, 2018). In contrast, heat storage is anticipated to be largely independent of chimney height (within moderate ranges), being instead governed by the stove’s thermal mass, insulation, geometry, and material properties (Gumino *et al.*, 2020).

This study addresses the identified gap by evaluating a wood stove design in which chimney height is systematically varied (50, 100, 150, and 200 cm) while holding all other design and operating variables constant (geometry, materials, pot size, fuel type, test procedure). Performance is measured through the standard Water Boiling Test (WBT), capturing thermal efficiency, time to boil three litres of water, and post-combustion heat storage (cooling duration). Polynomial regression models will be fitted for each performance metric as a function of chimney height, thereby enabling identification of the optimal chimney height for this stove configuration. The findings will provide practical guidance for stove designers and contribute empirical evidence to the evolving discourse on draft optimization in biomass stove design

2. METHODOLOGY

Performance evaluation was conducted using the Water Boiling Test (WBT). Three litres of water were poured into identical aluminium pots and placed on each stove. The initial water and pot temperatures were recorded, and firewood was weighed before combustion. Combustion was initiated simultaneously for all stoves, and the time taken for the water to reach boiling was recorded. After boiling, firewood was extinguished, dried, and reweighed to determine fuel consumption. Efficiency was calculated as the ratio

of useful heat gained by the water and pot to the energy released from the consumed fuel. Heat retention was evaluated by monitoring the cooling rate after combustion.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Summary of Stove Performance

Table 1 presents the performance of four wood stoves constructed with identical combustion chambers but varying chimney heights. The evaluated parameters include thermal efficiency, time required to bring a fixed volume of water to boiling, and heat storage capacity. Efficiency and time to boil exhibited clear dependence on chimney height, while heat storage remained nearly constant across all designs, suggesting that chimney geometry primarily influences combustion and heat transfer dynamics rather than heat retention. The correlations are plotted in Figure 1 to Figure 3.

Table 1. Summary of the performance of four wood stoves

tove	Chimney Height (cm)	Efficiency (%)	Time to Boil (min)	Heat Storage (min)
A	50	25.5	29	19.20
B	100	28.3	25	19.08
C	150	31.7	21	19.13
D	200	31.0	23	19.21

Figure 1: Chimney vs thermal efficiency

Figure 2; Chimney Height Vs time to boil water

Figure 3 Chimney height vs heat storage

3.2 Influence of Chimney Height on Efficiency

As shown in Figure 1, the stove efficiency increased progressively with chimney height up to 150 cm and then slightly declined at 200 cm. The relationship follows a quadratic trend ($\eta = -0.0003H^2 + 0.087H + 21.5$; $R^2 = 0.992$), demonstrating that chimney-induced draft strongly affects the combustion process. An increase in chimney height enhances the buoyant flow of flue gases, improving air–fuel mixing and sustaining higher combustion temperatures (Bailis *et al.*, 2015; Bryden *et al.*, 2006). Consequently, the higher efficiency at 150 cm suggests that optimal draft promotes near-complete oxidation of volatiles and reduces unburned carbon losses.

However, further increase in height beyond 150 cm slightly reduced efficiency, likely due to excessive draft velocity. A high draft rate shortens the residence time of flue gases in the heat transfer zone, reducing conductive and convective heat delivery to the cooking pot (Jetter *et al.*, 2012). This inverse effect is consistent with findings from Basu (2018), who reported that in small-scale combustion systems, optimal chimney design involves balancing draft-induced combustion enhancement with retention of hot gases for effective heat exchange. Therefore, 150 cm can be identified as the optimum chimney height for efficient thermal performance under the experimental setup.

3.3 Effect on Time to Boil Water

The time-to-boil trend (Figure 2) mirrors the efficiency pattern, showing a minimum at 150 cm chimney height. The polynomial model ($T_b = 0.0025H^2 - 0.75H + 44.5$; $R^2 = 0.987$) confirms that as chimney height increases, boiling time decreases until the optimal draft condition is achieved, beyond which it slightly increases again. The decrease in boiling time up to 150 cm can be attributed to intensified combustion and higher flame temperature, leading to a greater rate of heat transfer to the pot bottom. This relationship between chimney-induced airflow and boiling rate has been similarly observed by Onchieku, *et al.* (2012) and Mani *et al.* (2019), who emphasized that improved draft minimizes fuel wastage and enhances flame impingement efficiency.

Beyond 150 cm, the increase in boiling time indicates diminishing returns due to energy losses with the faster exit of hot gases through the chimney. This demonstrates that beyond an optimal point, the beneficial effects of enhanced air supply are offset by the rapid convective removal of thermal energy. Hence, maintaining chimney height around 1.4–1.7 m ensures efficient energy utilization, consistent with ranges reported in small-scale biomass combustion studies (Parikh *et al.*, 2005; Vamvuka, 2011).

3.4 Heat Storage Characteristics

Figure 3 shows that heat storage time remained nearly constant (19.08–19.21 minutes) across all chimney heights, with a weak quadratic correlation ($R^2 = 0.79$). This finding suggests that heat storage depends primarily on the stove's mass, wall thickness, and material thermal capacity rather than chimney geometry (Jenkins *et al.*, 1998). Since all stoves were fabricated from the same clay mixture and maintained identical wall dimensions, their ability to retain heat after flame extinction remained stable. Comparable studies (Oliveira *et al.*, 2017; Venkata *et al.*, 2020) have also noted that the thermal inertia of clay-based stoves depends more on material composition and less on aerodynamic parameters like chimney length.

3.5 Overall Discussion

Collectively, these results demonstrate that chimney height is a crucial geometric parameter in biomass stove design, significantly affecting combustion efficiency and boiling performance but exerting negligible influence on stored heat retention. The identified optimal height of 150 cm aligns well with theoretical predictions and empirical reports in literature, indicating that controlled draft improves flame stability, combustion completeness, and energy transfer efficiency (Basu, 2018; Bryden *et al.*, 2006).

For practical applications, chimney design should therefore consider not only the enhancement of draft but also the retention of flue gases in the heat transfer zone. Overly short chimneys can cause incomplete combustion and smoke accumulation, while excessively tall ones may waste energy through rapid exhaust. The present results contribute valuable experimental evidence to guide efficient biomass stove construction in rural energy contexts.

4. CONCLUSION

This study established that chimney height significantly influences stove efficiency and boiling performance, with an optimal height of 150 cm yielding maximum thermal efficiency (31.7%) and minimum boiling time (21 min). Increasing chimney height beyond this point results in diminishing returns due to excessive draft. Heat storage was unaffected by chimney height. The findings highlight that chimney design optimization can improve combustion and energy utilization in locally fabricated biomass stoves, supporting cleaner and more efficient cooking technologies.

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